

Notes

Metal Halide-Phosphorus Halide-Alkyl Halide Complexes : Reactions with Iron(III) Chloride

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THE reaction products of aluminium chloride, phosphorus trichloride and alkyl chloride have been used for the synthesis of organophosphorus compounds¹. Similar reactions with other metals were reported by Bullock *et al.*² and Puri *et al.*³ However, no work has so far been reported on iron(III) complexes. In view of the above it was thought of interest to study the reaction systems $\text{R}'\text{PCl}_2\text{-FeCl}_3\text{-R}'\text{Cl}$ where R is phenyl or chloride and R' is n-butyl, *sec*-butyl, *iso*-butyl, *tert*-butyl, *tert*-amyl, cyclohexyl and triphenylmethyl.

Experimental

Materials: Reagent grade anhydrous ferric chloride was used. Phenyl phosphorus dichloride (Fluka) was purified by fractional distillation in vacuo. Phosphorus trichloride (BDH) and triphenyl methylchloride (Fluka) were used as such. Alkyl

chlorides were prepared from respective alcohols using standard methods and dried over P_2O_5 and distilled before use. CS_2 (Pfizer) and CH_2Cl_2 (BDH) were dried and distilled. Since many of the starting materials and products are hydrolysed and oxidised readily, all manipulations were made in all glass vacuum apparatus with rigorous exclusion of air and moisture.

Syntheses of complexes: A weighed quantity of FeCl_3 was dissolved in 20-30 ml of a dry deoxygenated solvent (CH_2Cl_2 or CS_2) and small excess of phosphorus halide was added to the solution. Finally alkyl chloride was added and reaction vessel was stoppered and set aside until precipitation of the reaction product was complete. The order of adding the reagents was always kept the same. Excess of the reagents were used to minimise the chance for the formation of polymeric anions. The completion of the reaction takes from ten minutes to two days. The solvent was decanted and the precipitate was washed with solvent by decantation. The products (dark yellow coloured solids) were then dried in vacuo (1-2 mm) for $\sim 1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. Analytical data are listed in Table 1. The melting points of the solids were not sharp. They melted with decomposition between 180-200°.

Analyses: The chloride was estimated as AgCl by standard gravimetric method⁴. Iron was estimated as ferric phosphate⁵. For estimation of phosphorus, the compound was agitated with HNO_3 in presence of KMnO_4 , precipitated as ammonium phosphomolybdate, redissolved in ammonia and precipitated as magnesium ammonium phosphate after complexing the metal ion with excess of citric acid⁴.

TABLE-1

No.	Complex	Analysis			Calculated % of			Magnetic moment per Fe atom(BM) (μ)	Mössbauer* spectral data	
		Fe	P	Cl	Fe	P	Cl		ΔE_Q mm/sec	Isomer shift δ mm/sec
1.	$[\text{Bu}^n \text{PCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	14.08	7.78	62.94	14.24	7.9	63.29		0.65	0.39
2.	$[\text{Bu}^t \text{PCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	14.35	8.00	62.89	14.24	7.9	63.29	5.35	2.0	0.49
3.	$[\text{Am}^t \text{PCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	14.00	7.75	60.83	13.75	7.62	61.11	5.66	1.9	0.40
4.	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \text{PCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	13.28	7.35	59.05	13.35	7.40	59.35		0.55	0.40
5.	$[\text{Ph}_3\text{CPCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	10.00	5.50	43.53	9.86	5.46	43.82			
6.	$[\text{Bu}^s \text{PhPCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	12.90	7.03	48.77	12.87	7.14	49.04			
7.	$[\text{Bu}^t \text{PhPCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	12.88	7.09	48.80	12.87	7.14	49.04	5.70	1.2	0.40
8.	$[\text{Am}^t \text{PhPCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	12.58	7.02	47.33	12.47	6.91	47.50	5.83		
9.	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \text{PhPCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	12.23	6.90	46.00	12.14	6.73	46.26			
10.	$[\text{Ph}_3\text{CPhPCl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$	9.25	5.00	34.77	9.18	5.09	34.94			

*with respect to stainless steel

Physical measurements: Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by the Guoy method. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded with a Beckman Spectrophotometer with MgO as the reference reflector. Samples were prepared in a dry box and protected by cover slips.

Mössbauer spectra were taken at room temperature using a constant velocity cam drive set-up. The source was $5m\text{Ci Co}^{57}$ in stainless steel matrix.

The spectral region $500\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was examined using Beckman IR-20 infrared spectrophotometer and samples were prepared in nujol mull between potassium bromide plates. The infrared spectra in the region $200\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were taken at I.I.T., Delhi.

Results and Discussion

The products are fairly moisture sensitive and become sticky upon exposure to the atmosphere. These are insoluble in all common organic solvents but do dissolve in acetone with probable dissociation, as they are not recoverable as such after the removal of the acetone.

The complexes were taken to be univalent ionic species in agreement with the results obtained by Kinnear and Perren¹ and Bullock *et al.*² for $[\text{Bu}^t\text{PCl}_3][\text{AlCl}_4]^-$ and other such derivatives³. Further the Mössbauer and magnetic studies of iron(III) complexes in the present investigation also confirmed the presence of univalent anionic species.

The trichloro alkyl phosphonium cation, $[\text{R}'\text{PCl}_3]^+$ is expected to have 3A, and 3E, infrared active vibrational bands with C_{3v} symmetry and the cation $[\text{R}'\text{PhPCl}_2]^+$ should be further distorted tetrahedrally having C_s symmetry and 6A' and 3A' infrared active vibrational bands. For $[\text{RPCl}_3]^+$, a very weak band in the range of $785\text{--}775\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to $\nu(\text{P-C})$. A medium weak band in the range of $485\text{--}480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a strong band in the region of 640 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu(\text{P-Cl})$ vibrations. A weak band in the $215\text{--}210\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is due to $\delta\text{R}'\text{-P-Cl}$. These observations are in agreement with the results of Bullock *et al.*² who also observed the bands at 780, 482, 639, and 210 cm^{-1} for $\nu\text{P-C}$, $\nu\text{P-Cl}$, and $\delta\text{Bu}^t\text{-P-Cl}$ band for $[\text{Bu}^t\text{PCl}_3]^+$ cation.

In case of $[\text{R}'\text{PhPCl}_2]^+$ cation, strong bands in the region of 1440 and 1000 cm^{-1} can be due to $\nu\text{P-Ph}$ vibrations and are similar to those observed by Seel *et al.*⁴ A band near 780 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu\text{P-C}$ (tertiary carbon). Weak to strong bands in the regions of 615 and 500 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu(\text{P-Cl})$ vibrations. These results are in agreement with those prepared by Bullock *et al.*² for $[\text{MeB}_u^t\text{PCl}_3]^+$ cation.

The FeCl_4^- anion exists in many organic solvents and aqueous solutions, as well as in solid state. This has been reported as a tetrahedral complex anion⁷.

In the compounds of the present study, the U. V. and visible absorption bands of the tetrachloroferrate ion observed at 236, 308, 340 and $445\text{ m}\mu$ are comparable to the values of 240, 314, 362 and $447\text{ m}\mu$ observed for such compounds earlier^{8,9}. The i.r. spectrum of FeCl_4^- anion in these compounds shows a stretching mode at $375\text{--}385\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is also in agreement with the band observed for FeCl_4^- in $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3][\text{FeCl}_4]$ at 385 cm^{-1} .

Magnetic susceptibility measurements showed that these compounds were strongly paramagnetic with an effective moment ranging from 5.34 to 5.82 B. M. This value corresponds to five unpaired electrons (calculated spin-only value is 5.92 B. M.). The room temperature magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of some compounds are listed in Table 1.

The isomer shifts in the Mössbauer spectra of the compounds are in the range of 0.35 to 0.49 mm/sec at room temperature with respect to stainless steel which are suggestive of tetrahedral high spin complexes¹⁰. The quadrupole splitting, ΔE_Q is between 0.55 to 2.00 mm/sec . Further, as the compounds are highly sensitive to moisture, there was difficulty in uniform packing of the samples. This introduces Gol'danskii Karayagin asymmetry effect.

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